

INNOVATIVE POTENTIAL OF THE TEACHER

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8013023>

Jumanova Fatima Uralovna

Head of the Department of Preschool Education Methodology of Nizomiy Tashkent State Pedagogical University, Ph.D., associate professor

Annotation.

The article considers the types of innovative processes in the field of education, the main stages of the innovative process. The innovative potential of the teacher is analyzed.

Аннотация.

В статье рассмотрены типы инновационных процессов в области образования, основные этапы инновационного процесса. Проанализирован инновационный потенциал педагога.

The innovation process is aimed at improving the quality of the system into which innovation is introduced, and involves stimulating the participants in this process, changing their views from the position of innovation. An analysis of many studies has shown that two types of innovative processes in the field of education are currently distinguished according to the nature of their origin.

The first type is innovation that occurs largely spontaneously, without precise reference to the generating need itself, or without complete awareness of the entire system of conditions, means and ways of implementing the innovation process. Innovations of this kind are not always associated with the completeness of scientific justification, more often they are carried out on an empirical basis, under the influence of the requirements of the current situation. The teacher goes to innovation from his non-traditional experience, organized, as a rule, spontaneously.

The second type is innovations in the education system, which are the product of a conscious, purposeful, scientifically cultivated interdisciplinary activity. The result of such activity is innovative pedagogy. This type of pedagogical innovation is scientifically organized. It is the highest in relation to the first type in terms of theoretical understanding, significance and scale of the results.[2]

The peculiarity of the innovation process lies in its cyclicity. Cyclicity is manifested in the sequence of stages in which an innovation passes - this is the emergence, growth, maturity, development, distribution, saturation, routinization,

crisis, finish. Most researchers distinguish three main stages of the innovation process: generating an idea (in some cases, a scientific discovery), developing an idea in an applied aspect, and implementing an innovation in practice. M.M. Potashnik [1], noting that the innovation process has a complex structure, it is polystructural (diverse in its structure), identifies the following hierarchy of structures:

- activity - a set of components: motives - goal - tasks - content - forms - methods - results;

- subjective - the activity of all subjects of development: teachers, administration of an educational institution, scientists, parents and students (pupils), consultants, experts, representatives of educational authorities, sponsors, etc.;

- level - innovative activity of subjects at the international, federal, regional, district (city) and school (level of educational institution) levels;

- content - the birth, development and development of innovation in teaching, educational work, school management, etc.;

- life cycle, expressed in stages: emergence (start) - rapid growth (in the fight against opponents, routineists, conservatives, skeptics) - maturity - development - diffusion (penetration, distribution to all parts of the educational and management processes) - routinization - crisis - irradiation (modernization of innovation);

- managerial - the interaction of four types of managerial actions: planning - organization - leadership - control;

- organizational, including the following stages: diagnostic, prognostic, actually organizational, practical, generalizing, implementation.

All of the above allows us to conclude that innovation processes are systemic: they include many components, but their simple sum is insufficient without structural links and patterns that characterize the innovation process as a whole.

All innovative processes have their carriers. The researchers note that the definition of the basic concepts of pedagogical innovation cannot be complete without characterizing the people who innovate in the education system.

Such innovators (innovators) bring constructive novelty into pedagogical reality. Their creative abilities and personal qualities do not automatically and without changes replicate someone else's pedagogical experience. As a rule, the subjective factor plays a decisive role at the stage of development, implementation and dissemination of innovation. The teacher-innovator is the bearer of a specific innovation and at the same time the creator or modifier of it in the process of implementation.

According to researchers, innovative teachers can be both from the educational organization or institution itself (educators, teachers, administration), and from outside (representatives of educational authorities, scientific consultants, etc.).

Innovative teachers are characterized by a high intellectual potential, a desire for pedagogical research and a critical attitude to reality, including in their professional activities, a focus on solving problems and contradictions.

A number of studies indicate that in modern conditions it is not enough for an innovator to express only an idea or develop a new approach, it is important to implement this approach in a particular educational institution in relation to new social services, methods, technologies, technical teaching aids, etc., which is impossible without teachers having innovative potential. "The innovative potential of a teacher is a set of creative and cultural characteristics of a teacher's personality, expressing a willingness to improve pedagogical activity and the availability of means and methods to ensure this readiness. Innovative potential of the teacher includes the ability to perceive new information, enrich one's own professional knowledge, promotion of promising and competitive ideas, finding solutions to non-standard pedagogical problems and new methods for solving standard pedagogical problems.

The transition to new market and production relations, changes in the socio-cultural sphere raised a number of questions for the world community at the end of the 20th century about the need to determine guidelines that would allow the individual to successfully respond to unexpected, often changing conditions of the surrounding world and actively transform it within the framework of professional activity. A person who has chosen systematic intellectual knowledge as the goal and form of his activity, including professional, acquires the possibility of self-development through intellectual self-improvement and the creation of innovations.

Innovations do not change the types of activities, but their technological ability to use as a direct production force - the ability to reproduce new knowledge. These changes show the transition from the "material" to the "intellectual" economy - the knowledge economy. T. Sakaya notes: "We are entering a new stage of civilization, in which the driving force is the values created by knowledge" [3]. For this reason, modern society is called innovative: Innovation Driven Society.

The new model of society provides for the expansion of the functions of a "narrow specialization" worker to a "wide range" worker (generalist), who is able to analyze in order to identify a problem and find ways to solve it, creative synthesis

of information. According to the authors (B. Santo, T. Sakaya), an employee of a “broad range” is distinguished from an employee of a “narrow specialization” by the presence of a formed innovative culture, which allows us to conclude that in the modern world there is a directly proportional relationship between the presence of an innovative culture and the level of professional implementation. activities.

Outcomes from the above, the analysis of psychological and pedagogical research indicates a variety of explanations for the essence of pedagogical innovation. Researchers distinguish various essential features of this concept. The most common explanation for all explanations is that pedagogical innovation is a purposeful, controlled change that introduces new elements into the educational process. It has been established that the emergence of pedagogical innovations has an objective-subjective nature. Their appearance is due to the need to bring the goals, content, methods and forms of training and education in line with the constantly changing requirements of society for the individual.

1. Поташник М.М. (ред.) Управление качеством образования. Практикоориентированная монография и методическое пособие.— Москва: Педагогическое общество России, 2000. — 448 с.

2. Zulfiya Abubakirovna Dehkambaeva. Problems in sports activities possibilities of using technologies. Current research journal of pedagogics. 1 November 2021

3. T. Sakaya. The Value Created by Knowledge, or a History of the Future // New Industrial Wave in the West: Anthology/Ed. by V. L. Inozemtsev. Moscow: Academia, 1999.